

SAIBAGE

Sulfur-Aluminium Battery with Advanced Polymeric Gel Electrolytes

H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017

FET-Open – Novel ideas for radically new technologies

GA 766581

Type of action: RIA (Research and Innovation action)

Start date of the project: 01/11/2017

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D.5.1

List of possible Al alloys and inorganic electrolyte additives to prevent dendritic formation in the anode

Project partners

LOGO	Partner full name	Acronym
	Albufera Energy Storage S.L.	AES
	University of Leicester	UoL
	Scionix Ltd.	Scionix
	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
	Technische Universität Graz	TUG
	University of Southampton	UoS

DTU Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DTU
--	-------------------------------	-----

Deliverable Name: *List of possible Al alloys and inorganic electrolyte additives to prevent dendritic formation in the anode*

Led by: DTU

Partners: DTU, TUG

Date	Version	Author	Institution	Comments*
19/10/2018	1	Ivano Eligio Castelli Juan María García Lastra	DTU	final version for evaluation
05/02/2019	2	Ivano Eligio Castelli Juan María García Lastra	DTU	revised version following evaluation

* Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
R	PU	List of possible Al alloys and inorganic electrolyte additives to prevent dendritic formation in the anode	D.5.1-PU-20-2018	02/00	05/02/2019	2 / 6
This project has received funding from the European Union H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017 Grant Agreement N ^o 766581 . This document and its content is CONFIDENTIAL unless otherwise stated according to the EU rules and GA terms.						

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
DFT	Density Functional Theory

Content

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Computational Method.....	4
3. Results.....	5
4. Conclusions.....	6

Figure Index

Figure 1: Example of adsorption energy of codopants.....	5
Figure 2: Adsorption energy of an Al-atom on co-doped surfaces	6

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
R	PU	List of possible Al alloys and inorganic electrolyte additives to prevent dendritic formation in the anode	D.5.1-PU-20-2018	02/00	05/02/2019	3 / 6

This project has received funding from the European Union **H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017** Grant Agreement N^o**766581**. This document and its content is **CONFIDENTIAL** unless otherwise stated according to the EU rules and GA terms.

1. Introduction

One of the possible solutions to avoid the formation of dendrites on the Al-anode in Al-S batteries is to engineer the anode so that a uniform Al layer is formed during the cycling of the battery. We thus investigated various possible commercial and non-commercial dopants that could be included in Al. A candidate dopant has the properties of being unstable in the bulk of the anode, i.e. would always like to be exposed on the surface of Al. In addition, the dopant should prefer to be at an under-coordinated site which is more reactive and prone to form dendrites. The dopant should also increase the probability that the Al-ions depositing during the charging of the battery sits at an under-coordinated site, so that a uniform layer is formed.

The computational method presented below only analysed the influence of dopants in Al to prevent the formation of dendrites during the battery cycling. However, the method did not establish how those dopants should be added to the Al. This is because the method only took into account thermodynamic quantities and not kinetic properties. The route to introduce the dopants into Al, either by metallic alloying or through dopant salt additives in the electrolyte (this decision constitutes Milestone 5), was decided after the computation method predicted the optimal dopants. The original decision in Milestone 5 was taken by a thorough literature scrutiny, comparing how the optimal dopants predicted by the computational study had been added to other metals in previous works.

2. Computational Method

We performed state-of-the-art Density Functional Theory calculations to investigate the adsorption properties of dopants and Al-ions on different adsorption sites. The calculations were performed using the GPAW code and PBEsol as exchange-correlation functional. A K-point mesh of at least $2 \times 2 \times 1$ was used with a grid mesh of 0.2 \AA^{-1} . We considered the Aluminium (111) surface, which exposes a kink and an edge, as shown in the right of Figure 1. At least 10 \AA of vacuum was included and dipole correction in the direction normal to the surface. All structures were relaxed until the residual forces were below 0.05 eV/\AA . The different dopants considered are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. List of dopants included in the computational screening

Commercial dopants	Cu, Mg, Si, Sn, Zn, Mn
Non-commercial dopants	Bi, La, Ga, In, Sb, Ca, Ba

No electrolyte was included in the simulations. We performed two sets of calculations. 1) We calculated the formation energy of the alloy (or dopant, since the concentration is very low). In order to be stable the energy of the alloy should be negative. In particular, the most favorable position for an ideal dopant should be at the kink site in an Al Surface. 2) We estimated the adsorption energy of an additional Al atom that adsorbs in different positions on the doped surface. Ideally, this second Al should adsorb in the proximity of a kink, i.e. this energy adsorption on this site should be the lowest among all the considered sites. The adsorption at the kink should be favorable, but not too strong, otherwise it would be difficult to swap the position of the Al and dopant and allow the next Al to adsorb.

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
R	PU	List of possible Al alloys and inorganic electrolyte additives to prevent dendritic formation in the anode	D.5.1-PU-20-2018	02/00	05/02/2019	4 / 6

This project has received funding from the European Union **H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017** Grant Agreement N^o**766581**. This document and its content is CONFIDENTIAL unless otherwise stated according to the EU rules and GA terms.

Figure 1: Example of adsorption energy of codopants (commercial dopant: Zn, non-commercial dopants: Ga, In, and Bi). On the right, the dopants sites are indicated.

3. Results

None of the commercial and non-commercial dopants, if taken alone, contributed to increase the adsorption energy of Al at a kink site. The reason for this was that either the dopant adsorbed too strongly or too weakly. If it adsorbed too strongly, the dopant would disappear in the bulk of the anode and the beneficial effect would disappear. If it adsorbed too weakly, the dopant would not adsorb on the anode and there would be no improvement in the adsorption of Al. The main reason for the latter was the different size of the dopants that created instability in the surface. The situation was different if two dopants were placed together. A combination of a larger and smaller dopant succeeded in improving the reciprocal stability and increased the adsorption energy of an Al-ion. An example of adsorption energy of the codopants is shown in Figure 1, and of adsorption energy of an incoming Al-ion in Figure 2. An optimal combination showed a slightly negative adsorption at the Kink-Edge site (Figure 1) and an adsorption energy for an Al-ion close to the one of Al on pristine Al surface (green star, Figure 2). **In month 12 DTU suggested a combination of Cu-In, Si-In or Zn-In to the experimental partners (TUG) for experimental testing.**

All the optimal combinations of dopants include In. This resembles the combination of Bi and In as co-dopants in Zn anodes, which has been recently shown to be successful for dendrite suppression (see ChemSusChem 2018, 11, 1933 – 1941). In that work Bi and In were introduced in Zn as salt additives to the electrolyte. Due to the similarities of the Bi-In co-doping in Zn with the Cu-In, Si-In and Zr-In codoping in Al, in month 12 DTU recommended to TUG to use the addition of salt additives in the electrolyte as the strategy to introduce the dopants in the Al-anode (Milestone 5 delivered in month 12).

In month 12 TUG started the first experiments with the Cu-In co-doping. However, TUG was not been able to assess whether these dopants have a beneficial effect on preventing the formation of dendrites or not. This was due to the presence of a ~5nm layer of Al₂O₃ (alumina) on top of the Al-anode, which readily form in Aluminium surfaces even in an atmosphere with a few ppm of oxygen. In month 13 TUG started to work on the removal of this alumina layer by mechanical and electrochemical methods. At the same time, DTU started calculations on the effect of the presence

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
R	PU	List of possible Al alloys and inorganic electrolyte additives to prevent dendritic formation in the anode	D.5.1-PU-20-2018	02/00	05/02/2019	5 / 6

This project has received funding from the European Union **H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017** Grant Agreement N^o**766581**. This document and its content is CONFIDENTIAL unless otherwise stated according to the EU rules and GA terms.

of alumina on the stability of the different dopants in aluminium, which was not taken into account in the original calculations. The results of these new calculations obtained in month 13 revealed that the dopants are much less stable (by more than 4 eV) in alumina than in aluminium. Such a big difference has a positive side: alumina does not prevent the dopants from blocking the nucleation sites in aluminium. At the same time, it also points out that it would be extremely difficult to diffuse these dopants from the electrolyte to the aluminium through alumina, i.e. that the strategy of introducing the dopants through a salt in the electrolyte could be severely hindered, as corroborated by TUG experiments. Thus, after reviewing all the data, it has been decided to amend Milestone 5 and to change the doping strategy, moving to a direct metallic alloying for the dopant introduction in Al. TUG is currently working in that direction, which is showing promising preliminary results.

Figure 2: Adsorption energy of an Al-atom on co-doped surfaces (Zn+ Ga, In, or Bi) and pristine Al. The adsorption sites are indicated in the figure on the right.

4. Conclusions

After a computational screening of dopants DTU suggested in month 12 a combination of Cu-In, Si-In or Zn-In to the experimental partners (TUG) to prevent dendritic formation in Al. DTU suggested introducing these dopants in Al through a salt additive in the electrolyte (Milestone 5 at month 12). The decision was taken based on previous works in the literature in which In co-doping in Zn was achieved by salt additives in the electrolyte.

However, in month 13 TUG corroborated the difficulties to introduce the dopants in the Al anodes through electrolyte salt additives due to the presence of a five nm alumina layer on top of the aluminum. DTU has performed calculations to understand the alumina blocking and in view of all the results, it was decided to amend Milestone 5. Consequently, the dopants are being (and will be) introduced in Al through direct metallic alloying.

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
R	PU	List of possible Al alloys and inorganic electrolyte additives to prevent dendritic formation in the anode	D.5.1-PU-20-2018	02/00	05/02/2019	6 / 6
This project has received funding from the European Union H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017 Grant Agreement N ^o 766581. This document and its content is CONFIDENTIAL unless otherwise stated according to the EU rules and GA terms.						